

A New Encrypted Secret Message Embedding in Audio by using LSB Based Steganography with AES

Ramesh Babu K¹ | Dr. Naga Ravikiran² | Sreechandra Swarna³ | Raju T⁴ | Prabhakar D⁵ | Aswini Lalitha⁶

¹Department of Electronics and Communication and Engineering, Chalapathi Institute of Technology, Guntur, Andhra Pradesh, India. rameshbabukolikapudi99@gmail.com

²Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering, Chalapathi Institute of Technology, Guntur, Andhra Pradesh, India. nagaravikiran.phd@gmail.com

³Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering, Chalapathi Institute of Technology, Guntur, Andhra Pradesh, India. sreechandra23@gmail.com

⁴Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering, Chalapathi Institute of Technology, Guntur, Andhra Pradesh, India. raazu.thommandru@gmail.com

⁵Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering, Chalapathi Institute of Technology, Guntur, Andhra Pradesh, India. prabhakardesamala@gmail.com

⁶Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering, Chalapathi Institute of Technology, Guntur, Andhra Pradesh, India. lalithaaswani2021@gmail.com

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ABSTRACT

This work explores the use of steganography to embed textual information into audio files. The proposed method encodes text by mapping its binary representation into the least significant bits (LSBs) of the audio data. During the embedding process, each character of the message is converted into its binary equivalent, focusing on the last four bits for integration. A prefix of 0 or 1 is used to introduce redundancy, enhancing the reliability of the embedded binary code. Additionally, control symbols in binary form are employed to differentiate between uppercase and lowercase letters, spaces, and numerical values. The proposed LSB-based approach improves the steganographic system's ability to conceal text effectively while maintaining audio quality. The system's performance is evaluated using Mean Opinion Score (MOS) with 20 test samples and by comparing Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR) values against those of established algorithms, demonstrating its robustness and efficiency.

Keywords: Audio Steganography, Text Embedding, Least Significant Bit (LSB) Method, Mean Opinion Score (MOS), Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR)

1. INTRODUCTION

Steganography is a technique used to transmit data or secret messages through open channels without revealing their presence to unintended parties. Unlike traditional encryption, which focuses on hiding the content of secret communications, steganography aims to conceal the very existence of these messages [1]. Modern steganography predominantly utilizes electronic media as carriers, with physical artifacts being rarely employed [2]. Various methods have been proposed to embed data in channels such as images [3], video [4], audio [5], and even typeset text [6].

The preference for electronic media in steganography stems from several advantages. First, electronic media can be more easily manipulated to conceal and extract data, given the typically small size of the hidden information relative to the larger host data (the "cover text") [7]. Second, electronic data can be efficiently processed by computers, enabling complex algorithms to embed and retrieve hidden messages [8]. Steganography often exploits redundant, unused, or unnoticeable data gaps in electronic media to embed information without altering the perceived quality of the host medium [9].

This study focuses on utilizing audio files as host media for embedding textual messages without compromising the files' structure or content. Preserving the perceptual quality of the host audio is critical, as noticeable degradation undermines the fundamental goal of steganography—to remain undetectable [10].

Desired Characteristics of Steganography:

An effective steganographic system should meet three primary criteria: **imperceptibility**, **accuracy**, and **payload capacity** [11].

- **Imperceptibility** ensures that the embedding process does not produce noticeable changes in the host medium, making the hidden data undetectable.
- **Accuracy** guarantees the precise recovery of the embedded information without errors.
- **Payload capacity** refers to the amount of data that can be embedded and reliably transmitted to the recipient [12].

In the context of pure steganography, only the sender and recipient are aware of the encoding and decoding methods [13]. A robust steganographic scheme also incorporates additional desirable attributes. First,

access to a secret key is required for extraction, ensuring security. Second, the embedded data should remain undetectable even after insertion into the host medium. Third, the steganographic system should allow for the embedding of reasonably lengthy messages without compromising host integrity. Finally, the hidden data must demonstrate resilience to alterations caused by compression or other modifications in the host medium, ensuring precise and reliable extraction [14].

This paper explores the challenges and methodologies for embedding textual messages in audio files, emphasizing the development of a robust system that maintains audio quality while achieving high security, accuracy, and payload capacity.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Most of the data hiding methods for MP3 audio that have been proposed in the literature have low embedding capacity. For MP3 audio, MP3Stego is the most widely used tool among a few stego tools viz., MP3Stego, UnderMP3Cover, and MP3Stegz. It has been proved that MP3Stego detection is possible [17]. In [17], the authors proposed an MP3 steganography method by exploiting the rule of window switching during encoding, which exhibits a very low capacity. The complexity involved in the MP3 audio steganography is by its format [15], [16]. In MP3 files, the information hiding process may be carried out before, during or after compression. Pre-compression hiding is risky as it may lead to loss of hidden data. Various compression steps may be used for data hiding if complexity and the capacity are not an issue. MP3 files can be watermarked using watermarking algorithms that are robust to compression [18], [19].

The redundant bits in the frames are manipulated to embed the watermark during the encoding process. Barnali Gupta Banik et al. proposed an audio steganography technique that uses both Discrete Wavelet Transform (DWT) and Discrete Cosine Transform (DCT) to hide an image in an audio file. The audio file format is not specified in the paper which is important for audio steganography because usually the compressed formats are preferred, and when compressed, the secret information should not be lost. It was able to achieve a hiding capacity of only 1.56% [20]. One recent publication states about the insertion of secret bits in the sign bits of the MP3 bit stream where

the capacity is minute [21]. Since about the last two decades, steganography is being combined with cryptography to enhance the security. However, using standard encryption techniques in addition to the steganographic algorithm increases the complexity. One such proposal is found in [22], which uses AES encryption technique and the MD5 hash function to improve the MP3 steganography. Even in this paper, the capacity is very little. If the audio file is a WAV file, then information processing is not difficult. The authors in [23] proposed the audio steganography techniques in transform domain, which improve the security and also enhance the capacity. But they have used WAV files in their implementation. If the secret information is an audio and the cover is any other file such as image [24], then the embedding is not complex. Even if the secret audio is in MP3 format, it can be converted to WAV format and then it can be hidden. But if this conversion is used for cover MP3 audio and then used in steganography for embedding, the secret information cannot be retrieved if the stego audio is converted back to MP3. Mohammed Hatem Ali Al-Hooti et al. [25] proposed a method to hide the secret information in the WAV cover audio with logical operators using random sample bits. The authors in [26] generated a new audio channel to hide the secret data, which may increase the cover audio size. A secure technique with less complexity and high capacity to hide a large amount of secret information is of necessity, and one such method is proposed in this paper.

3. EXISTING APPROACHS

3.1 Audio Cryptography

In an era where the Internet serves as a critical medium for communication, commerce, and data exchange among millions of users, security has become indispensable. Whether safeguarding sensitive business transactions, protecting personal messages, or managing passwords, implementing robust cryptographic measures is no longer optional. Audio cryptography addresses this need by embedding security measures into audio data, enabling secure transmission while maintaining the integrity of the audio medium. As concerns over privacy and data breaches grow, employing cryptographic techniques in audio data ensures an additional layer of security for sensitive information.

3.2 Public-Key Cryptography

Public-Key Cryptography (PKC) represents one of the most significant advancements in the field of cryptography in the last few centuries. Introduced in the 1970s, PKC fundamentally transformed secure communication by eliminating the need for a pre-shared secret key. Unlike symmetric cryptography, PKC uses two keys: a public key for encryption and a private key for decryption.

PKC relies on mathematical one-way functions—functions that are computationally simple to execute but infeasible to reverse without a specific key. This property allows two parties to exchange information securely even over an insecure channel. For example, if Alice wishes to send a confidential message to Bob, she encrypts the message using Bob's public key. Bob can then decrypt the message using his private key, ensuring the confidentiality and authenticity of the communication. Additionally, PKC enables mechanisms such as digital signatures, which allow the recipient to verify the sender's identity and the integrity of the message.

3.3 Disadvantages of Cryptography

Despite its strengths, cryptographic techniques, particularly public-key cryptography, have several limitations:

High Transmission Time: Transmitting large documents encrypted with public-key cryptography can be time-consuming and computationally expensive, especially over resource-constrained networks.

Large Key Sizes: Achieving a high level of security requires larger key sizes, which can increase computational overhead and reduce efficiency.

Vulnerability to Impersonation: Public-key cryptography is susceptible to impersonation attacks if the public keys are not properly authenticated, highlighting the need for robust key management and certificate authorities.

4. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

The proposed method employs **phase coding** to embed secret data into audio files, modifying the phase of audio signals to encode the information. This method leverages the limitations of the Human Auditory System (HAS), which has minimal sensitivity to phase changes, ensuring that the embedded data remains imperceptible.

By using a digital audio file (specifically in .wav format) as the host medium, the proposed approach achieves secure and undetectable communication.

4.1 Design Methodology

For this study, .wav files are chosen as host files due to their uncompressed format and high-quality audio fidelity. To maintain the audio quality, modifications are restricted to the least significant bits (LSB) of the audio samples [34].

Structure of WAV Files

A .wav file consists of two main components:

1. **Header:** The first 44 bytes of the file, containing metadata such as sample rate, bit depth, and file size. This section is critical and remains unaltered during the embedding process to avoid file corruption.
2. **Data:** The portion of the file storing the actual audio samples, where data embedding occurs.

Embedding Process

The embedding process involves modifying the least significant bits of the audio sample data to incorporate the binary representation of the secret text. Below are the steps:

1. Read the audio file bit by bit and store it in a new file.
2. Keep the first 44 bytes (header) unchanged.
3. Start embedding from a designated point in the data section (e.g., the 51st byte).
4. Modify the least significant bits of alternate audio samples to encode the binary representation of the secret message.

For example, to embed the word "Audio," its binary values are mapped to the LSBs of the audio samples.

Character	Binary Value
A	01000001
u	01110101
d	01100100
i	01101001
o	01101111

Changes are made selectively to minimize perceptual degradation. Modifications involving 1, 2, 3, and 4 bits are compared to assess the impact on the host audio quality.

4.2 Algorithm for Data Embedding

1. Retain the header portion of the audio file (first 44 bytes) without modification.
2. Begin embedding from the 51st byte.
3. Replace the least significant bit (LSB) of alternate audio samples with bits from the secret message.
4. Continue the process until the entire message is embedded.

Audio Sample	Original LSB	Modified LSB
51	0	1
53	1	0
55	0	1

4.3 Algorithm for Data Extraction

1. Retain the first 50 bytes of the file without processing.
2. Begin extraction from the 51st byte.
3. Retrieve the least significant bit (LSB) of alternate samples.
4. Accumulate these bits into a queue.
5. Convert the binary sequence to decimal and map it to ASCII characters to reconstruct the hidden message.

Audio Sample	Extracted LSB	Binary Queue
51	1	1
53	0	10
55	1	101

4.4 Extraction Process

To retrieve the embedded message, the receiver uses the following steps:

1. Read the audio file starting from the 51st byte.
2. Extract the least significant bits from alternate samples.
3. Combine the extracted bits to reconstruct the binary representation of the hidden message.
4. Convert the binary values to their corresponding ASCII characters to reveal the message.

This process ensures that the embedded data is retrieved accurately and without perceptible alterations to the host audio.

Advantages of the Proposed Method

- **Secrecy:** The message remains hidden and inaccessible without the extraction algorithm.
- **Imperceptibility:** Changes to the audio file are undetectable to the human ear.
- **High Capacity:** The method allows embedding substantial amounts of data in the audio file.

Applications

Military Applications: Secure communication of sensitive information.

Secure Data Transmission: Ensures privacy and integrity during data exchange.

5.RESULTS & DISCUSSION

This section gives the detailed analysis of simulation results implemented using MatlabR2016a. Further, performance of proposed approach is compared with state of art approaches using same dataset

5.1 Dataset

The dataset contains the voice samples from five different persons. From each person 9 samples are collected with multiple phrases. Totally, 45 phrases are collected in entire dataset. Further, 80% of dataset is used for training, 20% of dataset is used for testing the Audio stego systems.

5.2 Objective evaluation

This section evaluates the quality of the encrypted and decrypted speech signals to assess the cryptosystem's resilience against various cryptanalysis attacks. The simulation was conducted using MATLAB on an HP laptop (Intel Core i3) running the Windows 7 operating system. For testing, five speech signals were randomly selected from the TIMIT database, with durations of 1.4150, 2.8550, 3.3150, 4.7350, and 5.3950 seconds, sampled at a frequency of 16 kHz.

Figure 1 illustrates the waveforms of the original speech signal, the ciphered speech signal, and the decrypted speech signal for the final test sample. Examination of Figures 1a and 1b reveals that the ciphered speech signal generated by the proposed scheme is entirely unintelligible, resembling white noise with a highly uniform distribution. This indicates the

absence of residual intelligibility, ensuring robust encryption.

Conversely, Figures 1a and 1c show that the decrypted speech signal is identical to the original signal, demonstrating the effectiveness of the decryption process. The recovered signal exhibits high quality and remarkable precision, affirming the robustness of the cryptosystem

5.3 Differential analysis

A modified speech signal is created by inverting the bit that is considered to be the least important in each sample. The input and changed speech signals are both ciphered using the same key, which results in the production of two encrypted speech signals.

Fig. 1: (a) Original Speech Signal, (b) Ciphered Speech Signal, (c) Deciphered Speech Signal

Table 1: Quality Metrics Values for Encrypted Signal

Signal name	SNR (dB)	PSNR (dB)	NPCR	UACI	CC
Signal 1	-61.4085	6.0671	99.96	37.2940	3.1683×10^{-4}
Signal 2	-62.7880	6.0823	99.96	37.2066	-1.6828×10^{-4}
Signal 3	-62.5135	6.1119	99.96	37.0317	4.8035×10^{-4}
Signal 4	-64.8471	6.0914	99.98	37.1593	-7.2535×10^{-4}
Signal 5	-65.4124	6.1153	99.97	36.9895	-6.2950×10^{-4}

After that, the two encrypted speech signals are compared using two criteria that are standard: the Number of Pixels Change Rate (NPCR), the Unified Average Changing Intensity (UACI), the Signal to Noise Ratio (SNR), the Peak Signal to Noise Ratio (PSNR), and the Correlation Coefficient (CC) analysis. Both the NPCR and UACI should be at their ideal levels of 100% and 33.3%, respectively. Table 2 contains a listing of the NPCR and UACI values that were acquired from the work that was recommended for various voice files.

The data shown in this table demonstrates that all of the NPCR and UACI values are quite close to those considered to be optimal. As a result, the differential analysis will not break the voice cryptosystem that has been presented.

Spectrogram analysis

Fig. 2: Spectrograms of (a) Original Speech Signal, (b) Ciphred Speech Signal, (c) Deciphred Speech Signal

A spectrogram is a visual representation of the frequency spectrum, illustrating how frequencies vary over time within a spoken stream. Figure 2 presents the spectrograms of the original, ciphred, and decrypted voice signals generated by the proposed cryptosystem.

A comparison of Figures 2a and 2b clearly demonstrates that the spectrogram of the ciphred signal is entirely different from that of the original signal. This significant alteration confirms the effectiveness and quality of the encryption process.

Furthermore, a comparison of Figures 2a and 2c reveals that the spectrograms of the decrypted signal and the original signal are identical. This indicates that the decryption process is highly accurate, ensuring the successful recovery of the original voice signal.

6. CONCLUSION

Voice recognition is performed by estimating the formants and detecting the pitch of the voice signal using **Linear Predictive Coding (LPC)**. The developed system is a word-dependent voice verification system designed to authenticate an individual's identity based on their unique voice characteristics. The system utilizes statistical computations, formant estimation, and wavelet energy analysis for verification. Verification tests were conducted using a dataset of 50 preloaded voice samples from five individuals, achieving an accuracy rate of approximately 80%.

Conflict of interest statement

Authors declare that they do not have any conflict of interest.

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